

of activation as calculated from the Arrhenius plot, is 6.5 kcal mol⁻¹.

The X-ray diffraction data of the product when compared with the known data for NaCl, suggest the presence of NaCl in addition to some other compounds. The experimental *d* values 3.22 (95), 2.75 (100), 1.99 (10), 1.75 (27), 1.62 (23), 1.40 (7), 1.28 (6), 1.22 (10) and 1.18 Å (12) correspond to the NaCl structure. Formation of NaCl suggests the stoichiometry of the reaction to be

However, the X-ray diffraction data for HgWO₄ could not be traced either from the powder diffraction file or from the literature.

The applicability of the linear equation shows that the reaction kinetics are controlled by the phase boundary reaction and the diffusion occurs unhindered⁴⁻⁶. The product layer is porous and does not offer any resistance to the diffusion. The low value of the energy of activation 6.5 kcal mol⁻¹ substantiates it to be a phase boundary controlled reaction. Substantial increase in *C* values with rise in temperature suggests vigorous initial reaction at the interface.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Professor P. S. Bassi, Department of Chemistry, Guru Nanak Dev University, for valuable discussions.

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Effect of Particle Size on the Kinetics of Thermal Dehydration of Silicic Acid Hydrogel

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Manuscript received 17 February 1984, accepted 3 May 1984

It is generally agreed¹ that the gelation of silica hydrogel is a function of the silica units. Silicic acid hydrogel, normally prepared by destabilisation of an aqueous solution of sodium silicate, has been used as a dehydrating agent in various processes.

The phenomena of crystallisation of silicic acid hydrogel which is analogous to the natural ageing of gels to hyalite, opal, chert, chalcedony, etc., has been studied² extensively by X-ray diffraction with refined DTA and dilatometric method. The surface properties of the silicic acid hydrogel are independent of the state of crystallinity³. It was observed⁴ that the first small losses of bound water occur at 150° followed by a continuous dehydroxylation above 380°.

The kinetic approach to the study of thermal decomposition of many hydrated materials depends on the rates of reaction and in addition gives basic information about the materials, their structure, surfaces and so forth. It was found⁵ that the rate constant during zeolitic dehydration followed an inverse relationship with the total water content of the samples and was explained in terms of position of water molecules in the lattice. It was also shown that the loosely bound channel water also influences strongly but is much less than that of coordinated water. The dehydration kinetics study on alumino-silicate hydrogel⁶, taking four different fractions concluded that the reaction followed formal first order kinetics. The activation energies showed little variation with respect to particle size and the absence of any particle size effect on the rate of dehydration was attributed to the highly porous structure of the gel. The deviation from the ideal behaviour at the later stage of dehydration was interpreted on the basis of structure.

In the present investigation an attempt has been made to correlate activation energies of different particle sizes of silicic acid hydrogel.

Experimental

Silicic acid hydrogel was synthesised by cation exchange technique. After proper ageing, they were processed in accordance with reported method⁷ to remove the extraneous impurities. The particle size fractions (-20+50), (-50+80), (-80+115), (-115+150), (-150+200) and (-200+300) mesh were prepared with utmost precaution. The materials were again washed, dried and stored at 32±1°. The kinetics of the dehydration process was studied by TG method⁸.

Results and Discussion

The isothermal dehydration curves (Figures not shown) showed exponential behaviour and as such first order kinetics was suggested. The initial water concentration (*L*_∞) which can be dehydrated at the experimental temperature and also the rate constant *k*₁ for the initial stage of dehydration was calculated⁹ using equation (1)

$$\text{Log } \Delta L = \frac{-k_1 t}{2.303} + \text{log } L_\infty [1 - \exp(-k_1 \Delta t)]. \quad (1)$$

Where ΔL is the difference between the mass loss at time (*t*+ Δt) and *t*, time interval Δt

TABLE 1 - VALUES OF RATE CONSTANT (k_1) AS DETERMINED FROM LOG ΔL vs TIME PLOTS

Hydrogel	Size fraction	k_1 min ⁻¹ at °C			
		100	130	160	190
Silicic acid	-20+50	0.0794	0.1912	0.2818	0.4215
	-50+80	0.0782	0.1910	0.2814	0.4216
	-80+115	0.0780	0.1908	0.2810	0.4210
	-115+150	0.0778	0.1916	0.2808	0.4212
	-150+200	0.0784	0.1910	0.2815	0.4208
	-200+300	0.0798	0.1918	0.2820	0.4204

TABLE 2 - VALUES OF L_∞ AS DETERMINED FROM GUGGENHEIM EQUATION

Hydrogel	Size fraction	Initial wt. of sample = 0.5 (g). Mean L_∞ (g) at °C			
		100	130	160	190
Silicic acid hydrogel	-20+50	0.1150	0.1238	0.1248	0.1250
	-50+80				
	-80+115				
	-115+150				
	-150+200				
	-200+300				

Fig. 1. Arrhenius plots for silicic acid hydrogel of different size fractions for the initial stage of dehydration.

1. ○ -20+50 mesh
2. ● -50+80 "
3. △ -80+115 "
4. × -115+150 "
5. * -150+200 "
6. ⊙ -200+300 "

between two sets of readings being kept fixed at a value greater than twice the time for 50% dehydration. Using equation (1), the rate constant was calculated from the slope of linear plot of $\log \Delta L$ vs t . Knowing Δt and having obtained k_1

from the slope, L_∞ was determined from the intercept on the log axis (Figures not shown). The Guggenheim plots and the values of k_1 and L_∞ are recorded in Table 1 and 2. The activation energy was calculated from the usual Arrhenius plots using the rate constants (Fig. 1).

Gel water is normally characterised by loose bonding with which it is attached to the frame work. Most of the non-crystalline hydrogels contain colloidal water which may be regarded as the extreme case of broken bond water in which the particle size of the solid to which the water is linked is extremely small.

The L_∞ values as determined for the size fraction were found to be nearly the same at a given temperature as expected theoretically, since any deviation in particle size will not alter the final loss at infinite time but might alter the rate of dehydration. Again both k_1 and L_∞ were found to be direct function of temperature which means that the reaction rate and the amount of water expelled from the gel increased with the increase in temperature of heat treatment.

The rate constant values are equal for the different particle sizes at all the temperatures. No positive effect of particle size was observed on the kinetics of dehydration.

From the nature of $\log [(L_\infty - L)/L_\infty]$ vs time curves (not shown for brevity), it was clearly evident that the whole course of reaction did not follow the first order kinetics. As such the limits of applicability of the first order law have been determined from the extent of linearity of these plots. The validity of first order law was found to be influenced slightly by the particle size of the experimental samples, i.e. with the decrease in particle size the extent of linearity increased only to a small extent. It varied between 65 to 81.4% (Table 3). This might

TABLE 3 - EXTENT OF VALIDITY OF FIRST ORDER LAW AS DETERMINED FROM LOG $[(L_\infty - L)/L_\infty]$ vs TIME PLOTS

Hydrogel	Size fraction	First order law as valid upto % dehydration at °C			
		100	130	160	190
Silicic acid hydrogel	-20+50	65.33	71.82	74.88	75.56
	-50+80	66.12	73.08	75.45	77.62
	-80+115	66.38	73.08	76.01	78.12
	-115+150	69.09	74.88	77.09	78.12
	-150+200	70.49	76.01	78.12	80.94
	-200+300	71.81	76.50	78.12	81.37

be due to the fact that with decrease in particle size, the water molecules remaining at the later stages of dehydration, were not influenced to a great extent by the decomposed material and as such extent of linearity increased. It appears that the particle size has practically no influence on the dehydration rates and as such final stage of dehydration was not undertaken in this case.

The calculated values of activation energy from Arrhenius plot (Fig. 1) are presented in Table 4.

TABLE 4—VALUES OF ACTIVATION ENERGIES FOR INITIAL STAGE OF DEHYDRATION

Hydrogel	Size fraction	Activation energy kcal mol ⁻¹
• Silicic acid	-20+50	5.95
	-50+80	6.18
	-80+115	5.95
	-115+150	6.17
	-150+200	5.72
	-200+300	6.17

The activation energy values clearly demonstrate the absence of any effect of particle size. Thus no positive effect of particle size was observed on the kinetics of dehydration.

The results of the present study show that (i) particle size has practically no influence on the dehydration rates, (ii) with decrease in particle size, the extent of linearity increased only to a small extent and (iii) no positive effect of particle size was observed on the kinetics of dehydration.

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Effect of Addition of D(+) Glucose on the B-Z Oscillating Reaction

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Manuscript received 30 December 1982, revised 16 September 1983, accepted 17 June 1984

BELOUSOV-Zhabotinsky^{1,2} oscillating reaction has been well studied³⁻⁶ for the last few years.

In this communication, the effect of addition of D(+)-glucose, a typical reducing agent, on this reaction has been studied in the presence and absence of it. Gallic acid⁷⁻⁹ and citric acid² have been used as organic substrates and in both the systems, the changes in induction period, time period *etc.* on addition of glucose have been studied in details. Attempts have been made to explain the experimental results in terms of Field, Körös and Noyes (FKN) mechanism¹⁰.

Experimental

In the reaction with citric acid, solid glucose was taken in the reaction vessel. Separate solutions of ceric ammonium sulphate, potassium bromate and citric acid were prepared in sulphuric acid. Ferroin was used as an indicator and the reaction was triggered by the addition of citric acid solution. In case of gallic acid system, solid gallic acid was taken in the reaction vessel and solutions of sulphuric acid, glucose and potassium bromate were added. Here also ferroin was used as an indicator. Use of Ce^{IV} ions was however, unnecessary in this case and the reaction was triggered by the addition of bromate solution.

All solutions were so prepared and mixed that the concentrations in Tables 1 and 2 refer to the concentrations in media. In both cases the reaction mixture was stirred at a fixed rate. The sharp colour changes, blue to green in the case of citric acid, and red to light green in the case of gallic acid were utilised for recording induction period (appearance of first green colour), time period of oscillation, total number of oscillations and total time of oscillation. The experimental results have been summarised in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF D(+)-GLUCOSE ON B-Z SYSTEM CONTAINING GALLIC ACID AT 32°

[KBrO₃] = 0.1008 M, [H₂SO₄] = 1.1062 M, [gallic acid] = 0.0399 M, [ferroin] ≈ 0.0003 M

[D(+)-glucose] M	Induction period sec	Average of 3rd and 4th oscillation periods sec	Total no. of oscillations	Total time of oscillations sec
0.0948	94	7	4	25
0.0758	99	5	6	37
0.0472	123	6.5	9	78
0.0190	155	11	19	371
0.0095	146	17	44	1247
nil	156	20	82	2799

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF D(+)-GLUCOSE ON B-Z SYSTEM CONTAINING CITRIC ACID AT 29°

[KBrO₃] = 0.0153 M, [H₂SO₄] = 1.54 M, [citric acid] = 0.457 M, [ferroin] = 0.0007 M, [Ce^{IV}] = 0.0037 M

[D(+)-glucose] M	Induction period sec	Average of 3rd and 4th oscillation periods sec
0.0580	46	34.5
0.0390	62	42
0.0166	66	58
nil	71	93

Results and Discussion

The experimental results reveal that with both citric and gallic acid the induction period and the oscillation period decrease with increasing concentrations of glucose. For oscillation period, the average of 3rd and 4th oscillation periods has been considered as the first one or two oscillations are anomalous in many systems. In the case of gallic